

Nucleophilic Reactions of 2-Methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones with 2-Indolinones

R. S. VARMA* and (Miss) PREETI GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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2-Methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone undergoes nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions with different indolinones leading to 2-(3-methylene-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (2a-e). Similarly, *N*-methylindolinones react with 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone to give 2-(3-methylene-1-methyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (4a-e). Mannich reactions were performed on 2 with formaldehyde and morpholine/piperidine to give 2-(3-methylene-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (3a-e). The compounds have been characterised by ir, nmr and mass spectral data.

IN continuation of our work on the nucleophilic reactions of 2-indolinones², we report herein the nucleophilic reactions of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones with 2-indolinones. The 2-methyl group owing to its proximity with two electronegative nitrogen atoms behaving as a nucleophile, adds to 3-carbonyl group of 2-indolinones. The intermediate carbinol thus formed undergoes dehydration to yield 2 (Scheme 1). Thus nucleophilic attack of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone with 2-indolinones

Scheme 1

H, b; y=4-Cl, c; y=5-Cl, d; y=6-Cl, e; y=5-CH₃,
Scheme 2

and their *N*-methyl-2-indolinones leads to 2 and 4 respectively. The structures of 2 have been confirmed by preparing suitable morpholino/piperidino-methyl analogs (3; Scheme 2). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir, nmr and mass spectral data (Scheme 3)

Scheme 3

Experimental

2-[3-Methylene(substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (2): A mixture of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone¹ (1; 0.005 mol) and substituted-isatin (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting crystalline solid was washed well with methanol (Table 1).

2-[(3-Methylene-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (3): To 2 (0.005 mol) dissolved in dimethyl formamide (5 ml) was added formalin (1 ml) and morpholine (1 mol) with stirring. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 10 min, and then allowed to remain at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid product was washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform–petroleum ether (b.p. 80–100°) (Table 1).

Similarly, different piperidino analogs (Table 1) were synthesised.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl no	Compd. no	X	Yield %	M p °C	Mol. formula
1	2a	—	68	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
2	2b	—	65	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
3	2c	—	71	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
4	2d	—	65	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
5	2e	—	71	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
6	3a	O	61	220d	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
7	3a	CH ₃	61	>260	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄
8	3b	O	58	210	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
9	3b	CH ₃	58	188	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
10	3c	O	56	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
11	3c	CH ₃	55	>260	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
12	3d	O	59	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
13	3d	CH ₃	58	>260	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
14	3e	O	60	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
15	3e	CH ₃	56	>260	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄
16	4a	—	55	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
17	4b	—	51	170–75	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
18	4c	—	52	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
19	4d	—	51	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
20	4e	—	61	>260	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Compound sl. no. 7, δ 1.48 (6H, (CH₃)₂), 2.5 (4H, N-(CH₂)₂), 3.96 (3H, CH₃), 4.35 (2H, N-(CH₂-N)), 6.9–8.4 (12H, ArH) and 8.9 (1H, CH); sl. no. 8, $\nu_{\max}$ 1730 (C=O ester), 1720 (C=O quinazolinone), 1700 (C=N and C=C), 1610 (C=N, C=C), 1120 (C-O-C) and 770 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 9, δ 1.46 (6H, (CH₃)₂), 2.5 (4H, N, (CH₂)₂), 3.91 (3H, CH₃), 4.34 (2H, N-CH₂-N) and 6.2–8.5 (12H, ArH and CH); sl. no. 10, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1690 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1610 (C=N and C=C), 1125 (C-O-C) and 785 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl₂); δ 2.42 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.52 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 3.88 (3H, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, N-CH₂-N), 6.78–8.15 (11H, ArH) and 8.71 (1H, CH); sl. no. 11, $\nu_{\max}$ 1715 (C=O ester), 1675 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1600 (C=N and C=C) and 775 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 12, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1620 (C=N and C=C), 1120 (C-O-C) and 780 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 15, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N and C=C); sl. no. 16, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone) and 1610 (C=N and C=C); sl. no. 17, $\nu_{\max}$ 1730 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone) 1695 (C=O indolinone), 1605 (C=N and C=C) and 770 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 18, δ 3.18 (3H, NCH₃), 3.95 (3H, OCH₃), 6.8–8.4 (11H, ArH) and 8.85 (1H, CH); sl. no. 20, δ 2.21 (3H, ArCH₃), 3.01 (3H, NCH₃), 3.81 (3H OCH₃), 6.7–8.3 (12H, ArH and CH)

2-[(3-Methylene-1-methyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (4): A mixture of 1 and substituted-isatins (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3–4 h. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

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References

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